

**INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL AND FIRM VALUE OF QUOTED
CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM
POST ADOPTION PERIOD OF IFRSs**

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Abstract

This study was conducted to ascertain the influence of intellectual capital on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This was anchored on the fact that intellectual capital usually indicates the efforts of managers in committing funds to raise the level of knowledge in an organization. The ex-post facto research design was adopted because the study required secondary data. The population of this study was twenty (20) consumer goods companies quoted on the floor of Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG) as at 31st December, 2022. Fifteen (15) quoted consumer goods entities were sampled for the study purposively. Panel data were collected from the financial statements of the consumer goods companies sampled for the study. The variables of this study were firm value (FV) and intellectual capital (IC). The dependent variable was firm's value measured by Tobin's Q and the independent variables-the intellectual capital were represented by Human Capital (HC), Relational Capital (RC) and Structural Capital (SC). Company Size (CS) was used as a control variable. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression statistical tools. From the analyses, it was observed that HC, RC and SC had positive and insignificant influence on FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. In line with the findings, it was concluded that intellectual capital had significant influence on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies

in Nigeria. It was recommended that more investment should be made on all the variables of intellectual capital of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria to raise the value of the entities.

Keywords: Intellectual Capital; Firm Value; and Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

The continuous existence of quoted companies in any economy is to influence upon the macroeconomic variables of the economy. These include provision of employment, relative price stability, achieving balance of payment equilibrium and economic growth. Because of the role of quoted companies in ensuring improvement in economic growth and development, the need to raise certain performance indicators of these entities can never be over emphasized (Luckieta, 2021). This is because improvement in these performance indicators over the years usually guarantee growth in shareholders' wealth, who are regarded as the owners of the entities, as well as the survival of the companies. Performance indicators in companies are broadly classified into two known as book value performance indicators and market value performance indicators (Nuryaman, 2015). Book value performance indicators are those attributes that are often reported on published financial statements of quoted companies. They include profitability ratios such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), return on capital employed (ROCE), net profit margin and so on. Book value performance indicators also include total assets, total revenue, earnings per share (EPS) and book value of equity.

On the other hand, market value performance indicators are those attributes that show the worth of companies to the external parties. They are seen as indicators that portray the level of performance of entities in the marketplace. They include market price of shares and market price of equity. Firm value derives its name from the growth in both book and market value performance indicators. Thus, firm value could be computed based on the reported factors on published financial statements of companies known as book value indicators as well as market value indicators (Andreeva & Garanina, 2017). The need to link the activities of quoted companies to affect the economy of a country positively usually arouse the behaviours of managers to formulate and implement strategies that are capable of raising firm value of their companies. Quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria are some of these entities that are recognised as drivers of economic performance of Nigeria and the need to improve upon the firm value of these firms is of paramount importance.

The pace of contemporary business has shifted the activities of companies to be relying on knowledge-based economy. This is because technological advancement has taken fundamental position in the business environment of almost every economy in the world (Xu & Liu, 2020). The activities of companies are directed by the technical know-how of managers as well as the employees in the modern time.

The knowledge of individuals in organization has been seen and recognized by board of directors or managers of companies to elevate the value of entities. This is why intellectual capital has been recognised to be essential attribute used by managers of quoted companies in the modern business environment to influence upon different performance attributes which include firm value (Adegbayibi, 2021). Before now, the role of intellectual capital in influencing value of companies has not been brought to the notice of managers. This is why investment in marketing and distribution of companies' products were not considered so important and human capital development was not considered essential by managers. As ideas continue to grow and inventions are made, the need for intellectual capital was discovered.

Thus, the growth in knowledge brings about intellectual capital. For this reason, intellectual capital is defined as the overall knowledge acquired by companies which could assist the entities to achieve competitive advantage over others. Maintenance of intellectual capital is important in organization, but the efficiency of intellectual capital maintained is more essential (Suhendra, 2015). This is because managers of companies might invest huge sum of funds in raising intellectual capital of their entities through marketing and distribution of the companies' products and human capital development, but intellectual capital maintained is not affecting financial performance and firm value of their companies. So, the assessment of intellectual capital's soundness and strength is known by intellectual capital efficiency. Intellectual capital efficiency indicates the extent to which costs incurred by managers in raising intellectual capital have been able to affect financial performance and firm value of quoted companies in which consumer goods companies in Nigeria are not exceptional.

The key factors of intellectual capital recognised by researchers in the contemporary business world are human capital, relational capital, structural capital and capital employed. The factors of intellectual capital that are mostly related to human knowledge or intellect are human capital, relational capital and structural capital (Subaida & Mardiati, 2018). The strength of intellectual capital is usually seen in the factors of intellectual capital as they are capable of influencing upon various performance indicators of quoted firms positively and significantly. Several studies that have been conducted in this area of interest seem not to be adequate for the fact that influence of the variables of intellectual capital on firm value have not been established empirically especially in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Hence, the need for the present study.

The influence of intellectual capital is usually expected to affect firm value of companies positively. However, in some cases the opposite is often achieved. The target of managers in different accounting periods is to achieve growth or improvement in firm value using different accounting attributes that are within their control of which intellectual capital factors are included. The policies formulated and implemented by managers in different accounting periods are usually anchored on

how firm value could be improved using attributes like that of intellectual capital (Acuña-Opazo & Gonzalez, 2019). As firm value improves in any accounting period, managers of such companies are applauded for their action towards strategies implementation. Maintenance of intellectual capital of any company usually call for adequate investment in the area of manpower development known as human capital development and marketing and distribution of companies' products. Quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria are companies that operate with high level of manpower required from employees and the products manufactured by these entities need to penetrate throughout the existing and new markets (Hertina, Mayasari & Sulandari, 2020). Thus, there is need to improve upon intellectual capital of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria continuously.

Previous studies conducted in this area seem to be inadequate for the fact that they were mostly done on financial performance or profitability of companies. Also, in all these studies conducted, a subsector of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria regarded as consumer goods entities were rarely studied. In the post adoption era of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) by quoted companies in Nigeria, studies of the influence of intellectual capital on firm value of quoted entities are limited. This motivates the conduct of the present study. Of all the previous studies conducted to establish the influence of intellectual capital on value of quoted entities especially in Nigeria, there is still considerable argument and inconsistent results which conflict with other studies. Some of the previous studies claimed that intellectual capital had negative influence on firm value while others claimed that intellectual capital had positive and insignificant influence on firm value of entities. This calls for the need to empirically address the conflicting issues in the literature.

In contemporary business practices, managers of quoted entities are of the view that intellectual capital is very fundamental to drive performance indicators of their firms. For the reason, the idea of raising and maintaining sound intellectual capital have been adopted by managers of quoted entities, inclusive of Nigeria. This is why huge funds are invested by managers of these quoted entities, specifically to incur costs on human capital development, innovations, linking their companies to the external parties and raising the reputation and goodwill of their firms (Suherman, 2017). Prior studies on intellectual capital and firm value of quoted entities have shown that the idea of maintaining sound intellectual capital help to reduce the possibility of corporate failure and provide assurance to going concern status of the entities. This implies that sound intellectual capital maintained in an entity is capable of improving firm value positively and materially.

However, from the published financial statements of some quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, it seems that share price, which is an indicator of firm value, stated over the years are not growing meaningfully but with fluctuating pattern despite the claim of managers of these entities to have maintained ideal intellectual capital that should have affected firm value (market price of shares) of these entities.

According to Ismail (2020), poor performance in terms of firm value is usually traceable to policies and strategies formulated and implemented by managers of the entities and usually affect the wealth of shareholders. It is on this note that the researcher is in doubt whether the development of intellectual capital by managers of quoted consumer goods in Nigeria has influence on firm value of the entities by taking into consideration the period of 2013 to 2021. The main objective of the study was to ascertain the influence of intellectual capital on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Firm Value and Measurement

Firm value is described as the perception of investors towards companies in terms of stock price, assets accumulated, profitability, market value of equity or market capitalization (Suherman, 2017). It is an essential concept in the literature of accounting and finance because it describes the worth of a company in the markets or in terms of the indicators reported on financial statements (Ahmed, Khurshid & Yousaf, 2019). The critical aspect of book value is the worth of an entity in the markets. Based on this definition, it could be viewed that firm value is broadly classified into book value performance and market value performance. Book value performance indicators are those accounting variables that support the creation of shareholders' wealth (Salehi & Zimon, 2021). They are often reported on the financial statements of entities which include profits, assets and total equity.

The market value performance indicators are those variables that define the growth of an entity in terms of the price of shares, market value of equity or market capitalization which support the maximization objectives of shareholders' wealth (Sardo & Serrasqueiro, 2017). According to Lusy, Budiyanto & Riduwan (2020), the market value performance indicators are usually considered when talking about firm value because they are not affected by unrealistic nature of financial statements. When firm value is viewed based on market perception, it means that the indicators are influenced by attributes reported on financial statements such as size of assets, capital structure, the level of sales revenue, liquidity, profitability and the total knowledge or intellectual capital possessed by the company.

Firm value could be measured by market price to book value ratio, market value of equity, market capitalization and the model of Tobin's Q (Suherman, 2017). The magnitude of firm value depends on the method used in its computation and in this case, it could be viewed that empirical studies are affected by the indicators of firm value. The model of Tobin's Q has been considered as an important method of computing firm value because it includes both variables of market value and that of the book value because of inadequate market performance data. It is computed as the aggregate market value of equity and book value of debt divided by total assets of entities (Salehi & Zimon, 2021). In this study, Tobin's Q model is used as a yardstick of firm value.

2.1.2 Overview of Intellectual Capital

Intellectual capital is seen as the aggregate of knowledge possessed by an entity from its activities of investment and continuous operation (Nuryaman, 2015). In the view of Andreeva & Garanina (2017), organization is expected to acquire knowledge in attracting more customers, strengthening the skills of employees and improving upon the internal operation. The drive to operate in accordance with the modern requirements of business is why resources are needed to be invested to improve upon the intellectual capital of organization. When intellectual capital of an entity is improved, it is expected that potential customers are attracted to the products or services of the company, employees' productivity is improved as well as the approach of handling tax in organization. In the opinion of Luckieta (2021), intellectual capital is understood to be an interesting resource in organization that could influence several financial performance indices including profitability and value. This is because of the relevance of knowledge in modern business activities as compared with the ancient mode of conducting business. In the recent time, intellectual capital is expected to be improved in an organization to enable them to meet their expectation, or their strategic objectives drawn from the mission statement.

As the level of intellectual capital is improved in an organization, it is possible to say that the company must be one that is growing in terms of how the products or services are known in the market, how equipped the employees are in terms of handling tasks and the level of strength possessed by the company in their operating processes. Intellectual capital is an aspect of knowledge-based economy that is highly needed in the modern business practice. In the opinion of Pasaribu, Purnamasari & Hapsari (2012), knowledge possessed by organizations is meant to transform the phase of the organization as well as expanding the scope. This is why intellectual capital is so essential that modern companies ensure that resources are invested to improve on the key variables. Quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria are some of those entities that need to improve upon their level of intellectual capital for the purpose of reaping the anticipated benefits accrued. The key factors of intellectual capital are human capital, relational capital and structural capital. For intellectual capital to be improved, the level of these variables must be influenced positively (Luckieta, 2021).

2.1.3 Measurement of Intellectual Capital

Intellectual capital could be measured by human capital, relational capital and structural capital. These key variables of intellectual capital are recognised by scholars in accounting and finance (Xu & Liu, 2020). This simply means that for when intellectual capital in an organisation is to be developed, the critical attributes to consider are development of human capital, relational capital and structural capital. The three attributes of intellectual capital are discussed accordingly:

- i. **Human Capital:** Human capital is defined as the variable of intellectual capital that is associated with the level of skill and knowledge possessed by

employees in organization (Adegbayibi, 2021). The investment of companies in training and development of employees is associated to improving upon human capital which is a variable of intellectual capital. When training and development of employees in organization is effective, it is expected that human capital is improved and when human capital is raised, several financial performance indicators must be improved (Suhendra, 2015). The strategies of managers to raise human capital in an organization are always traced to training and development of employees which are meant for the job-related activities and general education. Employees are expected to be equipped for both the job-related tasks and academically sound because modern business activities are volatile where academic achievement is essential. Human capital is calculated as valued added divided by expenditures incurred on employees or sometimes regarded as human resources costs (Subaida & Mardiati, 2018). Value-added is often seen as the difference between output and inputs of organization excluding human resource cost (Utami, 2018).

According to Acuña-Opazo & Gonzalez (2019), output in intellectual capital perception is regarded as the total revenue while input is regarded as total costs excluding human resource costs. When value-added is higher and greater than expenditures on training and development of employees, it could be said that human capital is created in such organization as well as improving intellectual capital. On the other hand, when value-added is less than expenditure incurred on training and development of employees in organization, it could be described that human capital is not created from the costs incurred on the training (Hertina *et al.*, 2020). When human capital is not created adequately based on the enormous expenditure committed on training and development of employees, managers could reduce their spending on such training as this does not impact positively on the entire growth of the organization in terms of raising intellectual capital (Nguyen & Doan, 2020). For quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, the influence of human capital will be established on the value created from 2013 to 2021.

ii. Relational Capital: Relational capital is an attribute of intellectual capital that is associated with the level in which organization tries to take their products or services to the customers (Utami, 2018). It is associated with all forms of relationship created by the company between customers and other entities for the exchange of products or services. Relational capital is associated with the soundness or relationship maintained by a company with customers and other external entities. In ensuring that relationships are created about the products or services of a company, investment on marketing and distribution is required for a company to embark on (Suherman, 2017). This is because in effective marketing, the products and services of a company is known to the various customers in terms of quality and usage (Natsir & Bangun, 2020). Relational capital is that variables of intellectual capital that presents the products or services of a company to the various customers.

The higher the relational capital of a company, the higher the intellectual capital possessed by such entity. Intellectual capital is calculated as value-added divided by expenditure on marketing and distribution activities of a company. Value-added is the difference between revenue and total costs excluding expenditures on employees (Reschiwati, Syahdina & Handayani, 2020). When value-added is greater than expenditure on marketing and distribution of a company, it could be said that relational capital is created in the company and as such firm value is expected to be improved. On the other hand, when value-added is less than the expenditure on marketing and distribution expenses incurred by a company, it could be described that the relational capital generated from the investment of a company in marketing activities is minimal and as such the costs should be reduced in subsequent accounting period (Gallegos *et al.*, 2021). In this study, the influence of relational capital on value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria will be established to understand the extent to which investment on marketing activities of the entities has affected the overall growth of the companies.

iii. Structural Capital: Structural capital is a variable of intellectual capital that deals with the internal process of an organization (Sharma, 2018). The word structure is linked to how organization is organised internally to achieve its strategic objectives. Structural capital is concerned with the infrastructures or databases used as a supporting mechanism in delivering of tasks effectively and efficiently. It is basically meant to integrate the internal processes of an organization for the purpose of higher growth attainment (Ismail, 2020). Structural capital is meant to transform the phase of organization from the well-known traditional method to the modern method where the use of facilities to enhance tasks in organization are considered crucial. Structural capital cuts tangible and intangible assets acquired and accumulated in an organization (Jose & Silva, 2021). The tangible aspects of structural capital are associated with furniture, van and all other equipment used in the conduct of business activities.

On the other hand, the intangible aspect of structural capital is associated with facilities that could not be seen or touched but are utilised in the conduct of business. The innovation strategy and internal process of communication in an organization are all regarded as the intangible aspect of structural capital. Structural capital is calculated as total revenue minus operating costs or expenses incurred by a company in an accounting period divided by value-added. It is also calculated as outputs minus inputs including human resource costs divided by value-added in an accounting period (Putra & Ratnadi, 2021). Structural capital is expected to influence value of a company when adequate facilities are utilised in an organization. This is why this study is conducted to establish the influence of structural capital on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

2.1.4 Other Factors that Influence Firm Value

Aside from the variables of intellectual capital, there are critically other factors both internal and external that could influence firm value either positively or negatively (Natsir & Bangun, 2020). These attributes include company size, leverage and liquidity. Company size is regarded as size of asset or revenue accumulated or generated by a company. As the size of a company increases, firm value could be affected either positively or negatively depending on the composition of the size (Yunita & Prastiwi, 2021). Company size is usually measured by taking the logarithm of total assets or revenue (Kurniawan & Muharam, 2021). Leverage is defined as the liabilities or debts use in financing total assets of a company (Sundari & Setiany, 2021).

It is also regarded as the composition of debt and equity in capital structure of a company (Pratama, Setyadi & Innayah, 2021). When total debt of a company is higher than equity or the opposite, there is usually an implication on firm value. Financial leverage is measured by accounting ratios such as debt ratios, debt-to-equity ratio and long-term debt ratio. Liquidity of a company is defined as the short-term solvency of a company which is described as the difference between total current assets and current liabilities in an accounting period (Martins & Lopes, 2016). Liquidity is associated with the strength possessed by a company in responding to its short-term matured obligations or commitments in an accounting period. Liquidity position of a company maintained in an accounting period has implications on firm value and to ascertain the liquidity position of a company, accounting ratios such as current, quick and cash ratios are normally used (Pratama *et al.*, 2021).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Resource Based Theory

Resource based theory was developed and advanced by Barney (1991). The theory was developed to explain the key resources of organizations and how they are utilised to improve upon the various performance indicators in an organization. In the view of Xu & Liu (2020), the goals and objectives of any organization is achieved in line with the mission when adequate resources are made available. Resources of organizations are both financial and non-financial (Adegbayibi, 2021). Financial resources are the total cash, debts, equity and other short-term assets that could easily be translated or converted into cash in a shorter period used in running the activities of companies. a company that has adequate financial resources is expected to acquire the required assets to run the activities of the organization effectively (Suhendra, 2015). Financial resources help in the acquisition of non-financial resources in an organization (Subaida & Mardiaty, 2018). This is because when an entity has adequate financial resources, sound property, plant and equipment (PPE) could be acquired and employees with adequate skills and experiences could be employed in the organization to raise the productivity.

Also, other activities in organization could be handled effectively to raise the operating capacity of the company such as training and development of employees, effective marketing and acquisition of modern facilities (Utami, 2018). Non-financial resources are regarded as resources that are not expressed in monetary terms, but they supplement other resources used in an organization. Non-financial resources include total knowledge of organization which are sub-divided into employees' productivity or total workforce, the level of relationship created between the company and the customers, the reputation of the company and internal capacity of the company. According to Barney (1991), resource-based theory emphasizes on the importance of both financial and non-financial resources in influencing the overall growth of the entity. Based on this theory, the major activities that could help to improve upon the resources of an organization are broadly classified into four regarded as value, rareness, imitation and organization (Acuña-Opazo & Gonzalez, 2019). Value is associated with the possibility of raising the growth of an organization through the use of workforce or human capital acquired (Hertina *et al.*, 2020). It is also linked with the possibility of improving upon the various performance indicators of an organization through the use of total resources accumulated.

Rareness is known as the capability of influencing various attributes of organization to achieve competitive advantage among the rivalry entities. Imitation is linked with the tendency of not allowing the knowledge or strategies of organization to be emulated by rivalry companies. It is associated with the ability of securing intellectual properties of a company and not allowing an unauthorised entity to emulate. Organization is concerned with the level of the structure arranged and the usefulness of the structure in influencing the overall growth of the organization (Nguyen & Doan, 2020). This theory is related to this study because of the basic attributes that are linked to total knowledge possessed by a company which is known as intellectual capital. It helps to explain how the variables of intellectual capital could raise the productivity or growth of the entire organization. Growth of organization could be represented by firm value in this study where the total knowledge possessed from the various investments of the company is regarded as intellectual capital. On this note, this theory is adopted in this study.

2.3 Empirical Review

Related studies were reviewed such as:

Martins & Lopes (2016) examined intellectual capital and profitability: A firm value approach in the European companies. The study sought to evaluate the influence of firm value on profitability of European companies. Five hundred (500) European companies were sampled for the study. Intellectual capital was represented by human capital, structural capital and relational capital while firm value was measured by Tobin's Q. Panel data were obtained from the published annual reports of the entities and analysed using panel regression technique. The result of the analysis showed that the variables of intellectual capital exerted positive and material influence on firm value of the sampled European companies.

Suherman (2017) investigated the impact of intellectual capital toward firm's profitability and market value of retail companies listed in Indonesia stock exchange (IDX) from 2013 to 2016. The study covered the period of 2013 to 2016 and panel data were collected from the published annual reports and financial statements of ten (10) sampled entities on IDX. The key factors of intellectual capital used in the study were human capital, structural capital and relational capital. The sourced data were analysed using descriptive statistics and panel regression approach. The outcomes of the analyses indicated that intellectual capital had a significant influence on profitability and insignificant influence on market value. It was also found that only human capital had a significant influence on profitability and only human capital and structural capital had significant influence on market value of the companies studied.

Luckieta (2021) conducted a study on company value measurement through intellectual capital and firm size. The intention of the researcher was to examine the impact of intellectual capital and firm size on company value of real estate and property sectors of Indonesian Stock Exchange. The period of the study was between 2018 and 2019. The sample size of the study was made up of thirty-eight (38) companies listed in Indonesian Stock exchange (IDX). Relevant data were collected from the published annual reports and financial statements of the firms. From the analysis, it was observed that intellectual capital proxy by Value Added Intellectual Capital (VAIC) had positive and significant impact on the value of Company proxy by return on equity. It was also found that firm size had a negative but insignificant impact on the value of company. Hence, intellectual capital and firm size had positive and significant impact on company value.

Salehi & Zimon (2021) conducted a study on the effect of intellectual capital and board characteristics on value creation and growth. The essence of the study was to examine the impact of intellectual capital on board characteristics and value creation and growth. The period of the study covered 2012 to 2018. Panel data were obtained from the published annual reports and financial statements of listed Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE). The sourced data were analysed using multiple regression technique. From the results of the analysis, it was observed that the intellectual capital of the board members had no influence on companies' value and growth.

Sundari & Setiany (2021) studied the influence of intellectual capital and environmental disclosure on firm value. The study was conducted to examine the influence of intellectual capital and environmental disclosure on firm value. The intention of the researchers was to empirically investigate the influence of intellectual capital and environmental disclosure on firm value of companies studied. Fifty-four (54) entities were drawn and sampled for the study. The key variables used in the study were VACA, VAHU, STVA and RCE. Firm value was measured by Tobin's Q. Panel data were collected from the published annual reports and financial statements of the sampled entities from the period of 2017 to 2019. The relevant data sourced were analysed using descriptive statistics and regression analytical tool. The outcomes of the analyses showed that the components of intellectual such as VACA,

VAHU and STVA exerted material influence on firm value. It also found that RCE and environmental disclosure had a significant influence on firm value.

Yunita & Prastiwi (2021) empirically studied the influence of intellectual capital on firm value. The purpose of the study was to empirically ascertain the level of influence exerted by intellectual capital on firm value for the manufacturing companies studied. The study covered the period of 2017 to 2019 and the study relied on panel data obtainable from sixty-two (62) manufacturing entities whose shares were quoted on the floor of Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). Simple linear regression analysis was used to establish the influence of the variables of intellectual capital on firm value. The outcomes of the analyses indicated that intellectual capital had a significant influence on firm value of the quoted manufacturing companies studied.

2.3.1 Gap in the Literature

The studies reviewed showed that relevant studies on intellectual capital and firm value of entities were conducted in different economy and sectors. More studies were done on financial services institutions especially intellectual capital on profitability of firms. In the area of intellectual capital and firm value of entities in Nigeria, limited studies were observed. Also, it appears that studies on intellectual capital and firm value of sub-sectors of manufacturing companies in Nigeria such as quoted consumer goods are rarely conducted despite the essentiality of these entities on the economy of Nigeria. On this note, the present study will contribute extensively to the literature in the related area of interest.

3. METHODOLOGY

The nature of this study, which is quantitative, permitted the adoption of *ex-post facto* research design because it was considered suitable in the study. The use of this research design would direct the researcher's attention towards the collection of secondary data for intellectual capital and firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The population of this study was made up of aggregate number of consumer goods companies in Nigeria whose shares were quoted on the floor of Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG) as at 31st December, 2022. In an accordance with the information provided on the floor of NEG as at 31st December 2022, the quoted consumer goods entities were twenty (20) in number. For this reason, the population of this study considered was twenty (20) consumer goods companies quoted on NEG.

The sample size of this study was appropriately determined and drawn from the population of twenty (20) consumer goods entities quoted on the floor of NEG. The basis for determination of suitable sample size for this study was anchored on the availability of data set in relation to the variables of the present study. The purposive sampling technique was used to appropriately ascertain the sample size of fifteen (15) quoted consumer goods companies for the study.

The non-probabilistic method of sampling known as purposive sampling technique was suitably used because some of the consumer goods entities listed do not have published financial statements and share price as single companies with the same currency. With the possibility of obtaining published annual reports with financial statements with share price, fifteen (15) quoted consumer goods companies were drawn and sampled for the study for this study.

The source of essential data for this study was restricted to the sampled consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Precisely, the published financial statements of these consumer goods entities would be properly examined from the period of 2013 to 2021. The nature of the data was the panel data set. The panel data set also permitted the application of panel regression -technique.

The techniques for data collection in this study was secondary. This was because the research design stated had already pointed out clearly the type of study conducted as well as the kind of data required. The secondary data to be collected are those data that are obtainable from the sampled consumer goods companies' financial statements often prepared and published by the management of firms. The *a priori* expectation for all the independent variables including a control variable of company size on the dependent variable of firm value (Tobin's Q) were all positive. However, the measurement of all the variables were presented:

- i. $FV \text{ (Tobin's Q)} = (MVE+BVD)/TA$
- ii. $HC = VA/EEX$
- iii. $RC = VA/MDEX$
- iv. $SC = (VA-EEX)/VA$
- v. $CS = \text{Logarithm (TA)}$

Where: FV = Firm Value, MVE = Market Value of Equity, BVD = Book Value of Debt, TA = Total Asset, HC = Human Capital, VA = Value-Added = Revenue-Total Costs + EEX, EEX = Employees' Expenditure, RC = Relational Capital, MDEX = Marketing and Distribution Expenses, SC = Structural Capital and CS = Company Size.

The dependent variable in this study was Firm Value (Tobin's Q) where the independent variable regarded as intellectual capital was measured using Human Capital (HC), Relational Capital (RC) and Structural Capital (SC). Company Size (CS) was a control variable adopted. In accordance with objectives of the study and the expectation of the researcher, the empirical models of this study were stated:

$$\text{Tobin's } Q_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 HC_{ij} + \beta_2 CS_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.1)}$$

$$\text{Tobin's } Q_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RC_{ij} + \beta_2 CS_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.2)}$$

$$\text{Tobin's } Q_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SC_{ij} + \beta_2 CS_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.3)}$$

$$\text{Tobin's } Q_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 HC_{ij} + \beta_2 RC_{ij} + \beta_3 SC_{ij} + \beta_4 CS_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.4)}$$

The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression techniques. The descriptive statistics was meant to examine the nature of the sourced data in terms of minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation and so on. Other statistical techniques that were crucial in testing the models of this study as well as assessing how significant each of the predictors were to the dependent variable (Firm Value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria) were R^2 , Adjusted R^2 , p-value, t-statistic and F-ratio. Precisely, regression analytical tests were done based on 5% level of significance.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Data Analysis

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of the data collected for this study was to enable the researcher to evaluate the nature of the dataset for each of the variables of interest. These were computed and presented in Table 4.1:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Statistics	FV	HC	RC	SC	CS
Mean	62.188	2.237	20.672	0.859	7.699
Median	12.727	1.78	2.193	0.541	7.832
Maximum	952.03	19.959	655.239	66.052	8.684
Minimum	-15.55	-5.464	-47.941	-10.628	5.819
Std. Dev.	158.761	2.883	73.723	5.853	0.664
Skewness	3.843	2.756	5.971	10.25	-0.549
Kurtosis	18.235	16.286	45.338	115.932	2.559
Jarque-Bera	1638.02	1163.86	10885.1	74102.8	7.879
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.020
Observations	135	135	135	135	135

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023)

From Table 4.1, Firm Value (FV) had mean of 62.188. This indicated that the average of FV for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of this study was 62.188. The median of FV indicated the middle dataset of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study as 12.727. The maximum of FV indicated the highest data of consumer goods companies as 952.03. The minimum of FV showed that the lowest data of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was -15.552. The standard deviation of FV indicated that the fluctuations from mean during the period of study for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria was 158.76 and was high. The skewness of 3.8433 indicated that the distribution of FV was positively skewed during the period of study. The kurtosis of 18.236 showed that the distribution for FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was highly above

normal curve. The Jarque-Bera statistics of 1638.02 compared with its probability value (p-value) of 0.0000 indicated that the dataset of FV was not normally distributed.

From Table 4.1, Human Capital (HC) had mean of 2.2367. This indicated that the average of HC for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of this study was 2.2367. The median of HC indicated the middle dataset of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study as 1.7800. The maximum of HC indicated the highest data of consumer goods companies as 19.959. The minimum of HC showed that the lowest data of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was -5.4640. The standard deviation of HC indicated that the fluctuations from mean during the period of study for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria was 2.8825 and was high. The skewness of 2.7563 indicated that the distribution of HC was positively skewed during the period of study. The kurtosis of 16.286 showed that the distribution for HC of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was highly above normal curve. The Jarque-Bera statistics of 1163.9 compared with its probability value (p-value) of 0.0000 indicated that the dataset of HC was not normally distributed.

From Table 4.1, Relational Capital (RC) had mean of 20.672. This indicated that the average of RC for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of this study was 20.672. The median of RC indicated the middle dataset of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study as 2.1930. The maximum of RC indicated the highest data of consumer goods companies as 655.24. The minimum of RC showed that the lowest data of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was 47.941. The standard deviation of RC indicated that the fluctuations from mean during the period of study for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria was 73.723 and was high. The skewness of 5.9709 indicated that the distribution of RC was positively skewed during the period of study. The kurtosis of 45.338 showed that the distribution for RC of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was highly above normal curve. The Jarque-Bera statistics of 10885.1 compared with its probability value (p-value) of 0.0000 indicated that the dataset of RC was not normally distributed.

From Table 4.1, Structural Capital (SC) had mean of 0.8586. This indicated that the average of SC for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of this study was 0.8586. The median of SC indicated the middle dataset of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study as 0.5410. The maximum of SC indicated the highest data of consumer goods companies as 66.052. The minimum of SC showed that the lowest data of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was -10.628. The standard deviation of SC indicated that the fluctuations from mean during the period of study for quoted

consumer goods companies in Nigeria was 5.8526 and was high. The skewness of 10.25042 indicated that the distribution of SC was positively skewed during the period of study. The kurtosis of 115.93 showed that the distribution for SC of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was highly above normal curve. The Jarque-Bera statistics of 74102.8 compared with its probability value (p-value) of 0.0000 indicated that the dataset of SC was not normally distributed.

From Table 4.1, Company Size (CS) had mean of 7.6994. This indicated that the average of FS for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of this study was 7.6994. The median of CS indicated the middle dataset of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study as 7.8320. The maximum of CS indicated the highest data of consumer goods companies as 8.6840. The minimum of CS showed that the lowest data of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was 5.8190. The standard deviation of CS indicated that the fluctuations from mean during the period of study for quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria was 0.6639 and was high. The skewness of -0.5491 indicated that the distribution of CS was negatively skewed during the period of study. The kurtosis of 2.5586 showed that the distribution for FS of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria during the period of study was below normal curve. The Jarque-Bera statistics of 7.8792 compared with its probability value (p-value) of 0.0195 indicated that the dataset of CS was normally distributed.

4.1.2 Test of Multi-collinearity

The multi-collinearity between the predictors (independent variables) were tested by the researcher using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The results computed were presented in Table 4.2:

Table 4.2: Test of Multi-collinearity

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
C	29230.90	161.0470	NA
HC	23.40080	1.708295	1.063314
RC	0.038654	1.239875	1.148873
SC	5.361834	1.026160	1.004380
CS	494.6526	162.7476	1.192653

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023)

From the results presented in Table 4.3, it was observed that all the predictors had Centered VIF of less than ten (10). This indicated that the independent variables, including the control variable of CS, had no problem of multi-collinearity. In other word, it could be interpreted that the influence of individual independent variables on firm value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria was not the same with another independent variable in the model.

4.1.3 Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix for all the variables of this study were computed by the researcher to examine the coefficient of relationship among the factors. The results were presented in Table 4.3:

Table 4.3: Correlation Matrix

Correlation	CS	FV	HC	RC	SC
CS	1.000				
FV	0.233	1.000			
HC	0.197	0.090	1.000		
RC	-0.335	0.073	0.063	1.000	
SC	0.042	0.014	-0.041	-0.029	1.000
Probability	CS	FV	HC	RC	SC
CS	-----				
FV	0.0065	-----			
HC	0.0222	0.2968	-----		
RC	0.0001	0.3979	0.4695	-----	
SC	0.6284	0.8683	0.6382	0.7351	-----

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023)

From Table 4.3, the relationship between an independent variable and another independent variable was less than 60% (0.6). This indicated that there was no sign of multi-collinearity existing among the pairs of independent variables. The relationship between HC and FV was 9.04%, the relationship between RC and FV was 7.33%, the relationship between SC and FV was 1.44% and the relationship between CS and FV was 23.30%.

4.1.4 Test of Hypotheses

Under this sub-section, individual hypotheses were tested from the outputs of analyses done by the researcher using appropriate statistical tools. The Hausman Test conducted on the data with probability value of less than 5% ($p < 0.05$) revealed that the fixed effect regression technique was suitable in this study.

4.1.4.1 Hypothesis One

The fixed effect regression results were computed by the researcher and presented in Table 4.4:

Table 4.4: Fixed Effect Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	360.5428	250.5349	1.439092	0.1528
HC	2.458819	3.403120	0.722519	0.4714
CS	39.46491	32.45063	1.216152	0.2264
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.7722			
Adjusted R-squared	0.7414			
F-statistic	25.0072	Durbin-Watson stat		1.534395
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Dependent Variable=FV

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023)

From Table 4.4, Human Capital (HC) had a positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This was because the p-value indicated that HC was insignificant on FV ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$). The HC was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher. A percentage increase in HC brought about increase in FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Company Size (CS) had a positive and insignificant influence on FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The constant value of 36054.28% showed the level of FV as HC and CS were held constant and was insignificant ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$). The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.53440 showed that there was no first order autocorrelation in the model. R^2 indicated that 77.23% variation in FV was caused by the influence of HC and CS and Adjusted R^2 indicated that 74.14% variation in FV was attributed to the influence of HC in the model. The F-statistic of 25.007 ($\text{prob.} < 0.05$) indicated that the model was significant.

4.1.4.2 Hypothesis Two

The fixed effect regression results were computed by the researcher and presented in Table 4.5:

Table 4.5: Fixed Effect Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	380.8703	250.5727	1.519999	0.1312
RC	0.028547	0.138637	0.205912	0.8372
CS	41.46742	32.56002	1.273569	0.2053
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.771326			
Adjusted R-squared	0.740320			
F-statistic	24.87618	Durbin-Watson stat		1.631000
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable=FV

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023)

From Table 4.5, Relational Capital (RC) had a positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This was because the p-value indicated that RC was significant on FV (p-value>0.05). The RC was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher. A percentage increase in RC brought about increase in FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Company Size (CS) had a positive and insignificant influence on FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The constant value of 38087.03% showed the level of FV as RC and CS were held constant and was insignificant (p-value>0.05). The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.6310 showed that there was no first order autocorrelation in the model. R² indicated that 77.13% variation in FV was caused by the influence of RC and CS and Adjusted R² indicated that 74.03% variation in FV was attributed to the influence of RC in the model. The F-statistic of 24.876 (prob.<0.05) indicated that the model was significant.

4.1.4.3 Hypothesis Three

The fixed effect regression results were computed by the researcher and presented in Table 4.6:

Table 4.6: Fixed Effect Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	378.7603	250.0148	1.514951	0.1325
SC	0.316769	1.263684	0.250671	0.8025
CS	41.08140	32.45654	1.265736	0.2081
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.771366			
Adjusted R-squared	0.740364			
F-statistic	24.88176	Durbin-Watson stat		1.532175
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable=FV

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023)

From Table 4.6, Structural Capital (SC) had a positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This was because the p-value indicated that SC was insignificant on FV (p-value>0.05). The SC was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher. A percentage increase in SC brought about increase in FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Company Size (CS) had a positive and insignificant influence on FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The constant value of 37876.03% showed the level of FV as SC and CS were held constant and was insignificant (p-value>0.05). The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.5322 showed that there was no first order autocorrelation in the model. R² indicated that 77.14% variation in FV was caused by the influence of SC and CS and Adjusted R² indicated that 74.04% variation in FV was attributed to the influence of SC in the model. The F-statistic of

24.882 (prob.<0.05) indicated that the model was significant.

4.1.4.4 Hypothesis Four

The fixed effect regression results were computed by the researcher and presented in Table 4.7:

Table 4.7: Fixed Effect Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	364.0135	253.7170	1.434723	0.1541
HC	2.370701	3.493501	0.678603	0.4987
RC	0.012368	0.142007	0.087093	0.9307
SC	0.283045	1.274438	0.222094	0.8246
CS	39.89174	32.87633	1.213388	0.2274
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.772360			
Adjusted R-squared	0.737036			
F-statistic	21.86534	Durbin-Watson stat		1.635605
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable=FV

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023)

From Table 4.7, HC, RC and SC had positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This was because the p-value indicated that HC, RC and SC were significant on FV (p-value>0.05). Company Size (CS) had a positive and insignificant influence on FV of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The constant value of 36401.4% showed the level of FV as HC, RC, SC and CS were held constant and was insignificant (p-value>0.05). The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.6356 showed that there was no first order autocorrelation in the model. R² indicated that 77.24% variation in FV was caused by the influence of HC, RC, SC and CS and Adjusted R² indicated that 73.70% variation in FV was attributed to the influence of HC, RC and SC in the model. The F-statistic of 21.865 (prob.<0.05) indicated that the model was significant.

4.2 Discussion of the Findings

From Table 4.4, Human Capital (HC) had a positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in HC during the period of study resulted to an insignificant improvement in firm value of the entities studied. The result of the analysis in respect to HC was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher of the present study. When organizations invest adequately on human capital and the skills of employees are improved from the trainings received, the productivity of employees will be improved which will in turn influence positively and substantially on the growth of the company. When the investment of organization on the training

and development of employees does not yield meaningful result in terms of transforming the skills of employees, the overall productivity of organization could be affected negatively as the productivity of employees is not improved significantly.

When investment on training and development of employees does not yield the anticipated result, it means that intellectual capital in such organization is not influenced. This is the case in this study where the investment on training and development of employees does not influence firm value substantially. This study was not in line with the study of Suherman (2017) who investigated the impact of intellectual capital toward firm's profitability and market value of retail companies listed in Indonesia stock exchange (IDX) from 2013 to 2016 and discovered that human capital had significant influence on market value of the companies studied.

From Table 4.5, Relational Capital (RC) had a positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in RC during the period of study resulted to an insignificant improvement in firm value of the entities studied. The result of the analysis in respect to RC was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher of the present study. Investment in marketing activities of companies is expected to yield more results of creating relationship about the companies' products with various customers. In other words, marketing and distribution expenses incurred by a company are to create relationship and exposes the products and services of the organizations to the various buyers. When marketing and distribution costs incurred create more relationship with the customers, higher revenue is expected to be made and as such, it could be described that the level of intellectual capital of the company has improved.

On the other hand, when investment in marketing and distribution costs does not create more relationship by arousing the interest of the customers to acquire more products from the company, higher turnover might not be realised and as such it could be said that the level of intellectual capital of the company is not improved. In this case, relational capital might not influence firm value significantly as the case in this study. This study was not in line with the study of Martins & Lopes (2016) who examined intellectual capital and profitability: A firm value approach in the European companies and found that variables of intellectual capital exerted positive and material influence on firm value of the sampled European companies.

From Table 4.6, Structural Capital (SC) had a positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in SC during the period of study resulted to an insignificant improvement in firm value of the entities studied. The result of the analysis in respect to SC was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher of the present study. Improvement in structural capital is meant to improve the internal process or operating capacity of an organization to achieve higher efficiency. When

adequate investment is made to acquire modern facilities to improve upon the operating capacity of a company, it is certain that the overall growth of the company is improved significantly.

On the other hand, when adequate investment on internal process of a company is not made, the level of structural capital of the company might be minimal and as such, the value of the company might not be improved significantly. This is the case in this study where structural capital does not influence firm value meaningfully, which measured the overall growth of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The present study was not in line with the study of Suherman (2017) who investigated the impact of intellectual capital toward firm's profitability and market value of retail companies listed in Indonesia stock exchange (IDX) from 2013 to 2016 and confirmed that structural capital had significant influence on market value of the companies studied.

From Table 4.7, Intellectual Capital (HC, RC and SC) had combined and significant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in any of the attributes used in this study jointly influenced the firm value of the entities in Nigeria positively. Individually, the variables of intellectual capital might not exert significant influence on the growth or value of a company, but when the variables are put together or combined, significant influence could be achieved. When significant influence is achieved by combining the key variables of a subject matter on a dependent variable, it could be said that the effort put all together has yielded some level of results which could translate to growth of the company. This is the case in this study where individually the variables of intellectual capital exerted insignificant influence on firm value and by combining all the predictors together, significant influence was achieved.

This indicated that intellectual capital exerted significant influence on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. This study was in line with the study of Yunita & Prastiwi (2021) who conducted a study on influence of intellectual capital on firm value and confirmed that intellectual capital had a significant influence on firm value of the quoted manufacturing companies studied. Also, the present study was in consistent with the study of Luckieta (2021) who conducted a study on company value measurement through intellectual capital and firm size.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

The empirical results obtained were as follows:

- I. Human Capital (HC) had a positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria (p-value>0.05).
- ii. Relational Capital (RC) had a positive and insignificant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria (p-value>0.05).
- iii. Structural Capital (SC) exerted a positive and insignificant influence on Firm

- Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$).
- iv. HC, RC and SC had combined and significant influence on Firm Value (FV) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

The study was conducted to ascertain the influence of intellectual capital on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. From the analyses conducted, it was concluded that intellectual capital had a significant influence on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Individually, Human Capital (HC), Relational Capital (RC) and Structural Capital (SC) had positive and insignificant influence on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

From the result of the analyses and in line with the independent variables of this study, the following recommendations were suggested:

- i. More investment should be made in training and developing of employees in organizations to raise more human capital that could affect firm value significantly.
- ii. Marketing and distribution costs should be increased to improve upon the relational capital of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria as this will affect firm value substantially.
- iii. Investment of marketing and distribution activities should be monitored effectively in line with the marketing strategy to ensure that the anticipated benefit is achieved to influence the overall growth of the organization meaningfully.
- iv. More investment should be made to improve upon the internal capacity of the company for the purpose of improving upon structural capital of the entities as this could influence firm value substantially.
- v. More investment should be made on all the variables of intellectual capital of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria to raise the value of the entities.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

This study was conducted to examine the influence of the variables of intellectual capital on firm value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The empirical result derived from each variable of intellectual capital on firm value presented different result compared to the existing literature. The period considered in this study was different from other studies. The sector used in this study presented a different view of intellectual capital on firm value. several studies on intellectual capital were mostly on financial performance measured in terms of profit. Thus, this study has contributed to the existing literature in terms of the measurement of dependent variable, the sector used, and the empirical results obtained for both individual variables of intellectual capital as well as the combined variables.

5.5 Suggestions for Further Studies

This study was conducted based on the scope. Therefore, entire gap in the literature was not covered. For this reason, the following suggestions were made for the conduct of other studies:

- i. Intellectual capital and firm value of quoted services companies in Nigeria should be studied by other researchers.
- ii. Intellectual capital and firm value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria should be investigated by other researchers with the use of other proxies for market value.
- iii. Intellectual capital and firm value of listed firms in Nigeria should be investigated.

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